

WAVELET METHOD FOR TIME-FRACTIONAL CONVECTION-DIFFUSION EQUATIONS

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Abstract

In this paper, a new method based on the Bernoulli wavelets expansion together with operational matrix of fractional integration is proposed to solve time-fractional partial differential equations. The proposed method is very convenient for solving such problems, since the initial and boundary conditions are taken into account automatically. The suggested method reduces this type of equation to the solution of an algebraic system. They have been used in modeling turbulent flow chaotic dynamics of classical conservation systems.

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1. Introduction

Recently, fractional differential operators are indisputably found to play a fundamental role in the modeling of a considerable number of phenomena. Because of the nonlocal property of fractional derivative, they can utilize for modeling of memory-dependent phenomena and complex media such as porous media and anomalous diffusion.

2. Basic definitions

2.1. The fractional derivative and integral

Definition 2.1. *The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order $\nu \geq 0$ is defined as [4]*

$$I^\nu f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f(s)}{(t-s)^{1-\nu}} ds, & \nu > 0, t > 0, \\ f(t), & \nu = 0. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.2. *Caputo's fractional derivative of order ν is defined as [4]*

$$D^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(n)}(s)}{(t-s)^{\nu+1-n}} ds, \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

* speaker

2.2. Bernoulli wavelet The Bernoulli wavelet $\psi_{nm}(t) = \psi(k, \hat{n}, m, t)$ involve four arguments, $\hat{n} = n - 1$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, k is assumed any positive integer, m is the degree of the Bernoulli polynomials and t is the normalized time. They are defined on the interval $[0, 1)$ by [3]

$$\psi_{n,m}(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \tilde{\beta}_m(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$\tilde{\beta}_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{(-1)^{m-1}(m!)^2}{(2m)!} \alpha_{2m}}} \beta_m(t), & m > 0, \end{cases}$$

and $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. Here $\beta_m(t)$ are the well-known Bernoulli polynomials of order m [3].

3. Operational matrix of the fractional integration

The Bernoulli wavelets can be expanded into an M terms Bernoulli polynomials as

$$\Psi_{2^{k-1}M \times 1}(t) = \Phi_{2^{k-1}M \times M} B_{M \times 1}(t),$$

where Φ is the transformation matrix of the Bernoulli wavelet to the Bernoulli polynomials [3]. The fractional integral of Bernoulli polynomials vector can be written as

$$I^\nu B(t) = F^{(\nu)} B(t),$$

where $F^{(\nu)}$ is given in [3]. Therefore, the Bernoulli wavelets operational matrix of the fractional integration $P^{(\nu)}(I^\nu \Psi(t) = P^{(\nu)} \Psi(t))$, is

$$P^{(\nu)} = \Phi F^{(\nu)} \Phi^{-1}.$$

4. Problem statement and approximation method

We consider the following time-fractional convection-diffusion equation

$$\frac{\partial^\nu u(x, t)}{\partial t^\nu} + a(x) \frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial x} + b(x) \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} = f(x, t), \quad 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (1)$$

with initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = f_0(x), \quad u(0, t) = g_0(t), \quad u(1, t) = g_1(t). \quad (2)$$

For solving this problem, we approximate

$$\frac{\partial^{2+\nu} u(x, t)}{\partial x^2 \partial t^\nu} \simeq \Psi^T(x) U \Psi(t), \quad (3)$$

where $U = [u_{i,j}]_{2^{k-1}M \times 2^{k-1}M}$ is an unknown matrix which should be found. By fractional integration of order ν of Eq. (3) with respect to t , we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \simeq \Psi^T(x)UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) + \left. \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{t=0} = \Psi^T(x)UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) + \frac{\partial^2 f_0(x)}{\partial x^2}. \quad (4)$$

By fractional integration of order 2 of Eq. (3) with respect to x , and using Eq. (2) we have

$$\frac{\partial^\nu u(x,t)}{\partial t^\nu} \simeq (P^{(2)}\Psi(x))^T U\Psi(t) - x(P^{(2)}\Psi(1))^T U\Psi(t) + (1-x)\frac{\partial^\nu g_0(t)}{\partial t^\nu} + x\frac{\partial^\nu g_1(t)}{\partial t^\nu}. \quad (5)$$

By fractional integration of order 2 of Eq. (4) with respect to x and considering Eq. (2), we get

$$u(x,t) \simeq (P^{(2)}\Psi(x))^T UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) - x(P^{(2)}\Psi(1))^T UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) + \mu(x,t), \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mu(x,t) = g_0(t) + f_0(x) - f_0(0) - xf'_0(0) + x(g_1(t) - g_0(t)) + x(-f_0(1) + f_0(0) + f'_0(0)).$$

By fractional differentiation of order 1 of Eq. (6) with respect to x , we obtain

$$\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} \simeq (P^{(1)}\Psi(x))^T UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) - (P^{(2)}\Psi(1))^T UP^{(\nu)}\Psi(t) + \frac{\partial \mu(x,t)}{\partial x}. \quad (7)$$

Replacing Eqs. (4) - (7) in Eq. (1) and collocating this equation at the $2^{k-1}M$ zeros of shifted Legendre polynomials $P_{2^{k-1}M}(x)$ and $P_{2^{k-1}M}(t)$.

5. Illustrative test problems

Example 5.1. Consider the following time-fractional diffusion equation ([2])

$$\frac{\partial^\nu u(x,t)}{\partial t^\nu} - \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = 2\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(3-\nu)}t^{2-\nu} - 1\right), \quad 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (8)$$

where $u(0,t) = t^2$, $u(1,t) = 1 + t^2$, $u(x,0) = x^2$.

The exact solution to this problem is $u(x,t) = x^2 + t^2$. By solving this problem for $k = 2, M = 1$ we obtain the exact solution.

Example 5.2. Consider the initial boundary values problem of fractional partial differential equation of order ν ([1], [5])

$$\frac{\partial^\nu u(x,t)}{\partial t^\nu} + x\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} = 2t^\nu + 2x^2 + 2, \quad 0 \leq x, t < 1, 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (9)$$

where $u(0,t) = 2\frac{\Gamma(\nu+1)}{\Gamma(2\nu+1)}t^{2\nu}$, $u(1,t) = 1 + 2\frac{\Gamma(\nu+1)}{\Gamma(2\nu+1)}t^{2\nu}$, $u(x,0) = x^2$.

The exact solution to this problem is $u(x,t) = x^2 + 2\frac{\Gamma(\nu+1)}{\Gamma(2\nu+1)}t^{2\nu}$. By solving this problem for $k = 2, M = 1$ we obtain the exact solution.

TABLE 1. Comparison of absolute error for $\nu = 0.5, t = 0.25$ for Example 1.

x	<i>Ref.</i> [2]		<i>Our method</i>
	$J = 1, m = 3$	$J = 2, m = 2$	$k = 2, M = 1$
0.2	4.4×10^{-3}	8.8×10^{-2}	0
0.4	5.1×10^{-2}	9.8×10^{-2}	0
0.6	7.1×10^{-2}	3.4×10^{-1}	0
0.8	2.8×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-1}	0

TABLE 2. Comparison of absolute error for $\nu = 0.5, t = 0.5$ for Example 2.

x	<i>Ref.</i> [1]	<i>Ref.</i> [5]	<i>Our method</i>
	$m = 64$	$m = 25$	$k = 2, M = 1$
0.3	1.9×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-5}	0
0.5	1.0×10^{-6}	2.8×10^{-5}	0
0.7	1.7×10^{-3}	2.0×10^{-5}	0
0.9	1.7×10^{-2}	4.7×10^{-6}	0

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